

A green methodology of two phase micellar extraction of Cu^{II} via Schiff base complex formation

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Abstract : Systematic investigation on an off-line two phase micellar extraction (TPME) coupled with atomic absorption spectroscopic (AAS) measurement of copper as the separation-preconcentration tool is described in the present communication. The TPME behavior of copper using *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)ethylenediamine (salen), a Schiff base, as the complexing agent and Triton X-100 (TX-100) as the non ionic surfactant is optimized. The role of different salting-in and salting-out agents on the extraction behavior is evaluated. The limit of detection was found to be 0.82 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ with the standard deviation of 0.06 ($n = 6$). The recovery of copper was found to be >96%. The method was applied for determination of copper in aqueous (spiked, industrial waste water), soil samples and certified reference material.

Keywords : Two phase micellar extraction, copper, Schiff base, Triton X-100, AAS.

Introduction

Metals are the oldest toxins known to the environment and since are not subject to biodegradation and have infinite lifetime¹. They are particularly important as they originate from several sources both natural and anthropogenic. The borderline between essential and toxic nature is difficult to draw and the behavior of a metal depends on its load and influenced by the matrix. Discharge of copper containing waste into the environment, due to its wide use in various industries, leads to the natural imbalance of the ecosystem². Elevated level of copper in soil also affects the growth and metabolism of plants. The severe health disorder in humans results due to accumulation of copper in liver, brain, kidney and cornea³. Trace metal determination even with sophisticated analytical tools becomes critical as well as a challenging task which needs prior separation and/or preconcentration steps before analytical measurement.

The procedure of preconcentration can be viewed as an interference removal technique that arises from low sensitivity and poor selectivity of analytical methods as applied particularly to matrices that are typically complex as well as source of a wide variety of potential interferents⁴. Very low analyte levels are often to be deter-

mined owing to the low concentration at which the harmful action of some pollutant is exerted. During preconcentration the target species from a large sample is ultimately gathered in a small volume or surface area and the analyte concentration is therefore raised to detectable or determinable level.

Among the different preconcentration techniques of metals in aqueous solution, liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and solid phase extraction (SPM) including ion exchange are quite popular due to wide range of applications. Such processes suffer serious limitation in terms of cost effectiveness and/or environment friendliness. The LLE requires use of huge volume of toxic organic solvents and have problems of phase separation due to mutual solubility of phases. The main disadvantage of SPE is the generation of sludge or waste residue of post operation. In order to overcome these problems TPME is the right choice towards the development of green technology. TPME follows a green chemistry pathway⁵ as :

- (i) the surfactants are not toxic, not volatile, and not easily flammable,
- (ii) the process uses diluted solutions of inexpensive surfactant and
- (iii) there is generation of no waste.

Moreover, in comparison with other extraction procedures it is simple and efficient with high preconcentration factor as the solute is transferred to the small volume of the surfactant phase. The process finds application in the field of speciation analysis^{6,7}. The present report deals with optimization of an off-line TPME-AAS process for determination of copper in water and soil samples. Copper after complexation with salen was subsequently trapped in the surfactant rich phase (TX-100) at the temperature higher than the cloud point. Copper concentration in the TX-100 phase was determined by AAS. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt for preconcentration of copper-Schiff base via extraction into TX-100 phase.

Results and discussion

As a general protocol TPME proceeds via transfer of hydrophobic chelate produced in aqueous environment into the surfactant micellar phases. Thus, to ensure reliable quantitative separation and high preconcentration efficiency for the subsequent metal ion determination a thorough optimization of the chemical and operational parameters is required⁹⁻¹³.

Selection of the ligand and the surfactant :

The choice of a ligand lies in the formation of stable complex. In the present investigation salen, synthesised from ethylene diamine and salicylaldehyde, is used for complexation for the quick and easy preparation as well as for high and quantitative yield. Moreover, the complex formed is of simple stoichiometric composition and of hydrophobic nature that facilitate the transfer of the complex from aqueous to the hydrophobic core of the micellar aggregates. A typical surfactant used in TPME should have high density, low cloud point temperature and balanced hydrophobicity. Here, Triton X-100 (TX-100), the non ionic surfactant is used.

Effect of pH :

The solution pH is an important parameter factor controlling formation and stability of metal complex allowing its partition to the micellar phase. The extraction percent of Cu^{II}-salen complex was found to increase sharply with increase in pH from 2 to 4 and decreases below 80% beyond pH 5.5. The highest extraction was observed at pH 4.1 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on extraction.

Optimisation of surfactant concentration :

In order to form micelle aggregates the surfactant concentration in solution generally kept above its critical micelle concentration. A successful TPME demands a high enrichment factor through minimizing the phase volume ratio. Here, the surfactant concentration was varied from 10 to 20% and phase volume ratio was found minimum for a surfactant concentration of 12%. Next, in order to maximize the extraction efficiency the volume of the same surfactant solution was varied from 1 to 10 cm³. It is found that highest extraction was achieved using 3 ml of surfactant (Fig. 2). Hence, 3 cm³ of 12% surfactant was taken as optimum for maximum extraction (>96%) and highest enrichment.

Fig. 2. Effect of surfactant volume on extraction.

Optimization of equilibrium time and temperature :

The dynamic equilibrium between the micelle and the aqueous phase is a kinetically controlled process. In order to allow sufficient interaction between the solute and micelles, i.e. for equilibrium transfer of solute to the micellar core optimization of incubation time is required. It is found that maximum extraction is achieved for an incubation period of 25 min at and above the cloud point temperature (CPT). The enhanced solution temperature beyond CPT helps proper cloud formation, dehydration

of micelle and decreased phase volume ratio (micelle : aqueous). Within the studied temperature range (323 to 363 K), the highest extraction efficiency is reached at a solution temperature of 342 ± 2 K.

Effect of ionic strength :

Extraction of metal in the micellar phase is known to be influenced by the ionic strength of the medium via modification of cloud point temperature¹⁴⁻¹⁷. The role of electrolytes on the extent of copper extraction was evaluated using some common electrolytes viz. NaCl, KCl, KNO₃ and (NH₄)₂SO₄. A fixed concentration of electrolyte (2.0 mol dm^{-3}), in each case, was added to the solution prior to CPE. It is found that cloud point temperature and the extraction extent vary with addition of the electrolyte but in different extents depending on the nature of added electrolyte. Presence of neutral electrolytes viz. chloride, sulfate, carbonate typically depress the cloud point, due to their salting-out effect, in proportion to their concentration. The lower the lyotropic number of the electrolyte, the greater is the effect. On the other hand, salting-in type electrolytes, such as nitrate, iodide and thiocyanate, typically increase the cloud point temperature¹⁸. Addition of (NH₄)₂SO₄ provides lower cloud point temperature and highest extraction and is used as an effective salting-out agent in all subsequent TPME experiments. The change of CPT and the extraction percent of different salts are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Influence of added salt on CPT and percent extraction

Salt added	CPT (K)	Percent extraction (%)
-	342 ± 3	86.6
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	334 ± 2	96.0
KCl	337 ± 2	90.6
NaCl	338 ± 1	92.0
KNO ₃	359 ± 2	81.8

The trend of variation of cloud point temperature and the extraction percent with varying volume of (NH₄)₂SO₄ is presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. Smaller amount of (NH₄)₂SO₄ results insufficient extraction probably due to limited clouding. Larger amount of (NH₄)₂SO₄ beyond the optimum concentration, however, increases the aqueous phase solubility of the complex due to salting-out effect¹⁹ and hence the extraction decreases. There-

Fig. 3. Effect of salt on CPT.

Fig. 4. Effect of salt on extraction.

fore, the experiments are performed using a volume of 0.4 cm^3 (NH₄)₂SO₄ for maximum extraction.

Effect of viscosity :

The highly viscous surfactant phase, containing the metal complex, after phase separation, needs to be fed to the nebulizer of AAS. In order to facilitate aspiration and introduction of the surfactant solution into the nebulizer, 2 cm^3 methanol containing nitric acid (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) was added to the surfactant phase. For smaller added volume of acidified methanol, the solution density is not appropriate for aspiration, whereas for higher volume the signal is decreased due to dilution effect.

Interferences :

The interferences in CPE yield may arise from one or both of the complexation step and the determination step. Determination of Cu^{II} in presence of different cations and anions was made and the limit of tolerance was evaluated with a relative error less than $\pm 5\%$ (Table 2).

Analytical figure or merit :

Precision of the proposed method was evaluated from the standard deviation value of six replicate analyses of spiked samples. Nine equal portions the stock Cu^{II} solu-

Table 2. Interference of foreign ions on CPE of copper(II)

Ions added	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)
Na ⁺ , K ⁺	1000
Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺	500
Fe ³⁺ , Al ³⁺	50
Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺	20
PO ₄ ³⁻ , CH ₃ COO ⁻ , C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	100
EDTA	20

tion ($50 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$) was taken. The concentration of Cu^{II} in the first five portions was determined individually following the proposed method and the mean was calculated. Copper solution of definite concentrations was spiked with each of the remaining four portions of the stock and the concentration was evaluated for each case. Recovery of the Cu^{II} in the samples was found to be greater than 96% with a standard deviation less than 0.06 at the 95% confidence level for five degree of freedom (Table 3). The characteristic features of the proposed method are presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Determination of copper(II) in spiked samples

Sl. no.	Concn. ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)			Recovery (%)
	Mean	Spiked	Found	
1.	50.0	0.0	45.55 \pm 0.053	96.1
2.	50.0	1.0	48.91 \pm 0.058	95.9
3.	50.0	3.0	50.56 \pm 0.060	95.4
4.	50.0	5.0	52.58 \pm 0.059	95.6
5.	50.0	10.0	57.30 \pm 0.059	95.5

Table 5. Recovery and preconcentration of copper(II) from industrial waste, soil and alloy

Sample	Composition	Recovery (%)	Std. dev. ($n = 6$)	P.F.
Industrial effluent (Electroplating waste)	CN ⁻ : 0.2; NH ₄ ⁺ -N : 50; Cd ²⁺ : 18.01; Pb ²⁺ : 11.2; Zn ²⁺ : 4.0; Cu ²⁺ : 10.0; Cd ²⁺ : 14.0; Ni ²⁺ : 62.2; pH : 7.89; S.S : 100	95.9	0.057	35.2
Soil ^a (Industrial area)	pH : 7.86; Org C : 3.32; N : 21.2; Cd ²⁺ : 12.01; Pb ²⁺ : 8.4; Zn ²⁺ : 5.6; Cu ²⁺ : 14.3; Cd ²⁺ : 10.1; Ni ²⁺ : 37.9	95.3	0.048	33.9
Steel ^b	C : 0.22; Cu : 0.22; Mn : 0.74; Si : 0.31; Cr : 1.17; Mo : 0.51	98.1	0.054	35.9

^aIn mg dm⁻³, except for pH; ^bin %.

Table 4. Analytical features of the proposed method

Feature	Parameter
Regression equation	0.006 C ₀ \pm 0.008
Linear range ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)	2.7–123.0
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)	0.18 (3 σ)
Standard deviation	0.06
Preconcentration factor	36

C₀ = 50 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$.

Effectiveness and utility of the proposed method :

The validity of the process was evaluated using some standard alloy sample. The utility and effectiveness of the method were tested with some effluent of electroplating industry and soil sample. The preconcentration factor, calculated as the ratio of the concentration of copper after preconcentration to that prior to preconcentration, which gives the same absorbance peak area²⁰, 36 for Cu^{II}-salen complex was obtained (Table 5). The low standard deviation and high value of recovery suggests the process as effective one. The negative free energy change ($-\Delta G$) was found to be 6.49 kJ mol⁻¹.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The visible spectral measurements were performed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model Shimadzu, UV-2401PC). Copper concentration in solution was determined with a flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA1407) equipped with a standard burner and an

air-acetylene flame at the wavelength of 324.8 nm. Standard hollow cathode lamp was used as line source with a slit width 0.5 nm and lamp current 4.0 mA. The pH measurements were made with a Systronics pH meter (Model 335).

Reagents :

All solutions were prepared with deionized water. The reagents are of analytical grade and obtained from E. Merck, India. Stock standard solution of Cu^{II} was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of CuSO₄.5H₂O. Working solutions were prepared by proper dilution of the stock. Buffer solutions of NaOAc-HOAc and NH₄OH-NH₄Cl were used to maintain the pH of the solutions. The non-ionic surfactant, Triton X-100 was used without further purification. The Schiff base ligands were synthesized as per the literature²¹.

Synthesis of ligands :

The reported Schiff base ligand, salen, was synthesized via condensation of ethylenediamine with salicylaldehyde in 1 : 3 molar ratio under reflux condition in methanol for 2–3 h. The solids appeared on cooling were subsequently filtered, washed and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂. The ligands thus prepared were recrystallized and characterized by elemental analysis, melting point determination and spectral data.

Procedure for metal extraction :

In the present case of TPME an aqueous aliquot of 15 cm³ containing a definite proportion of Cu^{II} and the ligand, buffered at the desired pH was mixed with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and TX-100 of suitable concentrations. The solution was taken in a typical glass tube, shaken for 5 min and left to stand in a thermostatic bath at 348 ± 2 K for 25 min. The solution was cooled, immediately after clouding occurs, in an ice-bath. The surfactant rich phase became viscous and retained at the bottom of the tube. The aqueous phase was separated and the metal content in the surfactant rich phase, diluted with acidified methanol, was determined by conventional aspiration to AAS.

Conclusion :

Use of CPE procedure offers a unique technique for separation and recovery of Cu^{II} from aqueous solution which includes low cost, safety, preconcentration with high recoveries and very good extraction efficiency. The

method shows very negligible interference effect in presence of many diverse ions, both cations and anions under suitable experimental condition. The proposed method can be applied to the determination of copper via preconcentration in water and soil sample.

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